

I. Administrative Information

I.1 Contributors

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I.2 Research Project(s)

- **Project Name:** Examining the Relationship among Air Exceptional and Pollution Resources in Canadian Provinces
- **Project Abstract:** This project investigates how various pollution sources, such as industrial emissions and vehicle exhaust, affect air quality in different regions of Canada, focusing on urban and rural areas. Using data from the National Air Pollution Control System (NAPS) and the National Pollution Results Inventory (NPRI), the project aims to correlate pollutant levels with their sources. The outcomes include processed datasets and visualizations that highlight pollution trends and their implications for environmental policy.
- **Starting Date:** 2024-11-01
- **Ending Date:** 2024-12-05
- **Funder:** CIHR (Canadian Institutes of Health Research) <https://cihr-irsc.gc.ca/e/193.html>
- **Funding Status:** Applied
- **Grant Number:** TBD

I.2.a.6 Costs

- **Title:** Data Management and Processing Costs
- **Description:** This includes costs associated with processing, storing, and managing data from the National Air Pollution Surveillance (NAPS) and National Pollution Results Inventory (NPRI) datasets. These costs also include any resources used to ensure the data is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).
- **Currency:** CAD (Canadian Dollar)
- **Amount:** \$10,000 (estimated including expenses for data cleaning, storage, software tools, etc.)
- **Cost Allocation:** Ensuring findability, accessibility, interoperability, re-usability of data, and supporting management.

- **How This Cost Will Be Covered:** Funding grant (TBD)
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II. Re-using Data

II.1 Existing Data

- **Is there pre-existing data?** Yes
 - **Existing non-reference data sets considered for re-use:** NAPS and NPRI data sets
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III. Creating and Collecting Data

The data for this project will primarily come from existing environmental databases, specifically the National Air Pollution Surveillance (NAPS) and National Pollution Results Inventory (NPRI). These datasets contain information about air pollution levels, sources, and environmental variables across various Canadian regions.

In addition to these secondary datasets, new data may be collected to supplement the analysis, such as:

- **Surveys** assessing the respiratory health of individuals in urban and rural regions, focusing on communities affected by pollution.
- **Field Observations** from additional air quality monitoring sites in cities not included in the NAPS and NPRI datasets, using sensors or monitoring equipment.
- **Interviews** with local public health officials and environmental experts to gather qualitative data on pollution sources and their impact on health.

The goal of this data collection is to complement existing datasets with real-world health impact data, enriching the analysis and ensuring a more comprehensive understanding of air pollution's effects on public health.

IV. Processing Data

The data will be processed using a combination of Python and R for data cleaning, transformation, and integration. The steps involved in processing will include:

1. **Data Cleaning:** The NAPS and NPRI datasets will be cleaned by removing incomplete records and handling missing data. This will be done using Python (Pandas) and R to ensure data quality and consistency.
2. **Data Integration:** The data from multiple sources (e.g., air quality and health outcomes) will be integrated by matching them based on geographic identifiers

such as city names and province codes. Data will be stored in a SQL database to facilitate easy retrieval and further processing.

3. **Data Transformation:** Variables will be normalized where necessary, and continuous variables (such as pollutant levels) will be categorized into groups (e.g., "high", "moderate", "low") to facilitate analysis. Units will also be standardized across datasets.

This processing approach ensures that the data is clean, organized, and ready for statistical analysis.

V. Interpreting Data

The interpretation of the processed data will focus on identifying correlations and trends between air pollution levels and respiratory illnesses in Canadian cities. The interpretation process will involve:

1. **Statistical Analysis:** Regression models, including multiple linear regression, will be applied to examine the relationship between air pollution levels and respiratory illness rates. Other statistical techniques may also be used depending on the dataset's complexity.
2. **Visualization:** Data visualizations will be created using Python's Matplotlib and Seaborn libraries as well as Tableau to highlight key trends, outliers, and correlations in the data. These visualizations will be used to communicate the findings clearly and effectively.
3. **Manual Interventions:** Manual adjustments may be made to the dataset or the interpretation process to account for potential confounding factors, such as income levels, smoking rates, or weather conditions. These factors will be controlled for to improve the accuracy of the statistical models and ensure the validity of the conclusions.

This interpretation process will allow the identification of significant patterns and relationships between pollution and health outcomes, contributing to the understanding of air pollution's impact on public health.

VI. Preserving Data

- **Data Set:** Air pollution, economic activity, and respiratory illness: Evidence from Canadian cities, 1974–1994
- **Description:** This dataset contains monthly hospital admission rates for various lung diagnostic categories across 11 Canadian cities between 1974 and 1994. It also includes ambient levels of five common air contaminants (e.g., nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide, particulate matter, etc.), along with covariate data such as income, smoking rates, and meteorological variables

(temperature, humidity, etc.). This data was used to analyze the relationship between urban air pollution and respiratory health problems.

- **Identifier:** DOI: 10.1016/j.envsoft.2010.01.010
- **Will this data set be published?** Yes
- **Where will the data be published?** (To be completed after you choose the repository or platform, e.g., Zenodo, Dryad, etc.)
- **Licenses:** (Specify your licensing preferences, e.g., CC BY, CC BY-SA, etc.)

VI.1.a.5 Does this dataset contain personal data?

- No

VI.1.a.6 Does this dataset contain sensitive information?

- No
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VII. Giving Access to Data

- **Can all of your data become completely open over time?**
Yes, but with conditions or an embargo period as necessary.